

Addition of Thiophenol to Conjugated Imines

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Mercaptans add to double bonds in accordance with Markownikoff's rule in the absence of peroxides but in the presence of peroxides abnormal addition takes place^{1,2}. Stable thiol adducts have been obtained with α : β -unsaturated ketones³, α -alkyl acrylonitriles⁴, β -alkyl acrylonitriles⁵, and also with isolated C = N bonds⁶. No such addition reaction seems to have been carried on when azomethine group is in conjugation with C = C bond; this communication deals with such reaction studies.

N-Cinnamalaniline, prepared by condensing equimolar quantities of cinnamaldehyde and aniline in ethanol, m.p. 109°, had i.r. absorption at 970 cm^{-1} (CH = CH trans) and at above 1600 cm^{-1} (s) (CH = N)⁷. The n.m.r. spectrum (60 Mc. in CDCl_3) gave no signal above 3 τ . Equimolar quantities of cinnamalaniline and thiophenol in dry benzene at room temperature gave white crystalline solid which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1), m.p. 90-91°, in 80% yield. When two mols of thiophenol were used the same compound was obtained indicating that only 1 : 1 adduct formed. The possible addition reaction is indicated below :

The structure (I) is supported by elemental analysis, I.R., U.V. and the N.M.R. spectrum (60 Mc/Sec. CDCl_3). The I.R. spectrum of (I) showed band at 975 cm^{-1} (CH = CH trans) and the NMR spectrum indicated the olefinic protons as two doublets (J_{12} 16 cps) in the region 3-4 τ , thereby indicating the absence of azomethine group. One proton signal

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appeared as quartet at 4.9 τ which changed to doublet on shaking with D₂O. It was assigned to C₃ and doublet at 6.1 τ assigned to N-H which completely disappeared on shaking with D₂O. These spectral properties are in accordance with the previously observed 1,2 additions^{8a,b}.

Similar adducts were obtained when other conjugated imines were used containing nuclear substituents like *p*-Cl, *p*-Br, *p*-OCH₃, *p*-C₂H₅. All the adducts obtained are stable except (I) which, on long standing turns to brownish resinous mass.

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